

Data Model for IRISS

The SURVEY table stores information about each survey, such as the survey_id, survey_name, survey_description, survey_uri and predecessor_survey_id (survey waves).

The ITEM table stores information about each item (an item can be question, variable, code set, etc.), such as the item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri and cv_id.

The SURVEY_ITEM table is a joining table that connects SURVEYS and ITEMS table, representing which items are included in which surveys.

The ITEM_CROSSREF table stores the type of relationship between the two SURVEY_ITEMS. This helps in keeping track of the different types of cross-references between items.

Conceptual Data Model

SURVEY table:

- survey_id (primary key)
- survey_name
- survey_description
- survey_uri
- predecessor_survey_id

ITEM table:

- item_id (primary key)
- item_name
- item_type
- item_uri
- cv_id

SURVEY_ITEM table:

- survey_item_id (primary key)
- survey_id
- item_id
- item_order

CROSSREF_TYPE table:

- crossref_type_id (primary key)
- crossref_type_name

ITEM_CROSSREF table:

- crossref_id (primary key)
- survey_item1_id
- survey_item2_id
- crossref_type_id

CONTROLLED_VOCABULARY table:

- cv_id (primary key)

- term
- definition

Tabular Representation of Conceptual Data Model

SURVEY table

Column name	Data type	Description
survey_id	integer	Primary key identifying the survey
survey_name	text	Name of the survey
survey_description	text	Description of the survey
survey_uri	text	URI of the survey (optional)

ITEM table

Column name	Data type	Description
item_id	integer	Primary key identifying the item
item_name	text	Name of the item
item_type	text	Type of item (e.g. question, variable, code set)
item_uri	text	URI of the item (optional)
cv_id	integer	Foreign key referencing the CONTROLLED_VOCABULARY table

SURVEY_ITEM table

Column name	Data type	Description
survey_id	integer	Foreign key referencing SURVEY table
item_id	integer	Foreign key referencing ITEM table
item_order	integer	Order of the item in the survey

CROSSREF_TYPE table

Column name	Data type	Description
crossref_type_id	integer	Primary key identifying the crossref type
crossref_type_name	text	Name of the crossref type (e.g. "same variable", "related question")

ITEM_CROSSREF table

Column name	Data type	Description
crossref_id	integer	Primary key identifying the cross reference
survey_item1_id	integer	Foreign key referencing SURVEY_ITEM table (first item)
survey_item2_id	integer	Foreign key referencing SURVEY_ITEM table (second item)
crossref_type_id	Integer	Foreign key referencing CROSSREF_TYPE table

CONTROLLED_VOCABULARY table

Column name	Data type	Description
cv_id	integer	Primary key identifying the controlled vocabulary term
term	text	The term in the controlled vocabulary
definition	text	Definition of the term in the controlled vocabulary

ER Diagram

SQL Statements to create tables

```

CREATE TABLE `controlled_vocabulary` (
  `cv_id` int,
  `term` varchar(255),
  `definition` varchar(255),
  PRIMARY KEY (`cv_id`)
);

```

```

CREATE TABLE `item` (
  `item_id` int,
  `item_name` varchar(255),
  `item_type` varchar(255),
  `item_uri` varchar(255),
  `cv_id` int,

```

```
PRIMARY KEY (`item_id`),  
FOREIGN KEY (`cv_id`) REFERENCES `controlled_vocabulary`(`cv_id`)  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE `crossref_type` (  
  `crossref_type_id` int,  
  `crossref_type_name` varchar(255),  
  PRIMARY KEY (`crossref_type_id`)  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE `survey` (  
  `survey_id` int,  
  `survey_name` varchar(255),  
  `survey_description` varchar(255),  
  `survey_uri` varchar(255),  
  `predecessor_survey_id` int,  
  PRIMARY KEY (`survey_id`)  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE `survey_item` (  
  `survey_item_id` int,  
  `survey_id` int,  
  `item_id` int,  
  `item_order` int,  
  PRIMARY KEY (`survey_item_id`),  
  FOREIGN KEY (`item_id`) REFERENCES `item`(`item_id`),  
  FOREIGN KEY (`survey_id`) REFERENCES `survey`(`survey_id`)  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE `users` (  
  `user_id` int,
```

```
`user_name` varchar(255),  
`user_email` varchar(255),  
PRIMARY KEY (`user_id`)  
);
```

```
CREATE TABLE `item_crossref` (  
  `crossref_id` int,  
  `survey_item1_id` int,  
  `survey_item2_id` int,  
  `crossref_type_id` int,  
  `user_id` int,  
  PRIMARY KEY (`crossref_id`),  
  FOREIGN KEY (`survey_item1_id`) REFERENCES `survey_item`(`survey_item_id`),  
  FOREIGN KEY (`survey_item2_id`) REFERENCES `survey_item`(`survey_item_id`),  
  FOREIGN KEY (`user_id`) REFERENCES `users`(`user_id`),  
  FOREIGN KEY (`crossref_type_id`) REFERENCES `crossref_type`(`crossref_type_id`)  
);
```

[Sample data filled](#)

[SQL Statements](#)

Note: Schema has changed now; statements need to be updated

```
-- Inserting data into the SURVEY table  
INSERT INTO survey (survey_id, survey_name, survey_description, survey_uri)  
VALUES (1, 'National Survey', 'A national survey of households', 'https://example.com/national-survey');  
  
INSERT INTO survey (survey_id, survey_name, survey_description, survey_uri)  
VALUES (2, 'Regional Survey', 'A regional survey of businesses', 'https://example.com/regional-survey');  
  
-- Inserting data into the ITEM table  
INSERT INTO item (item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri, cv_id)  
VALUES (1, 'Age', 'Question', 'https://example.com/age', 1);  
  
INSERT INTO item (item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri, cv_id)  
VALUES (2, 'Education level', 'Question', 'https://example.com/edu', 2);  
  
INSERT INTO item (item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri, cv_id)  
VALUES (3, 'Income', 'Question', 'https://example.com/inc', NULL);
```

```
INSERT INTO item (item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri, cv_id)
VALUES (4, 'Gender', 'Question', 'https://example.com/gend', 3);
```

```
INSERT INTO item (item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri, cv_id)
VALUES (5, 'Job title', 'Variable', 'https://example.com/job', 2);
```

```
INSERT INTO item (item_id, item_name, item_type, item_uri, cv_id)
VALUES (6, 'Age Group', 'Variable', 'https://example.com/agegroup', 4);
```

```
-- Inserting data into the SURVEY_ITEM table
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (1, 1, 1);
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (1, 2, 2);
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (1, 3, 3);
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (1, 4, 4);
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (2, 5, 1);
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (2, 6, 2);
```

```
INSERT INTO survey_item (survey_id, item_id, item_order)
VALUES (2, 3, 3);
```

```
-- Inserting data into the CROSSREF_TYPE table
```

```
INSERT INTO crossref_type (crossref_type_id, crossref_type_name)
VALUES (1, 'Same Variable');
```

```
INSERT INTO crossref_type (crossref_type_id, crossref_type_name)
VALUES (2, 'Related Question');
```

```
INSERT INTO crossref_type (crossref_type_id, crossref_type_name)
VALUES (3, 'Similar Code Set');
```

```
-- Inserting data into the ITEM_CROSSREF table
```

```
INSERT INTO item_crossref (crossref_id, item1_id, item2_id, crossref_type_id)
VALUES (1, 1, 1, 1);
```

```
INSERT INTO item_crossref (crossref_id, item1_id, item2_id, crossref_type_id)
VALUES (2, 2, 4, 2);
```

```
INSERT INTO item_crossref (crossref_id, item1_id, item2_id, crossref_type_id)
VALUES (3, 4, 5, 3);
```

```
INSERT INTO item_crossref (crossref_id, item1_id, item2_id, crossref_type_id)
VALUES (4, 1, 6, 1);
```

```
-- Inserting data into the CONTROLLED_VOCABULARY table
INSERT INTO controlled_vocabulary (cv_id, term, definition)
VALUES (1, 'Example', 'example');
```

```
INSERT INTO controlled_vocabulary (cv_id, term, definition)
VALUES (2, 'Education', 'A level of education attainment');
```

```
INSERT INTO controlled_vocabulary (cv_id, term, definition)
VALUES (3, 'Gender', 'A persons gender identity');
```

```
INSERT INTO controlled_vocabulary (cv_id, term, definition)
VALUES (4, 'Age Group', 'A persons age group');
```

Sample data

SURVEY table:

survey_id	survey_name	survey_description	survey_uri
1	National Survey	A national survey of households	https://example.com/national-survey
2	Regional Survey	A regional survey of businesses	https://example.com/regional-survey

ITEM table:

item_id	item_name	item_type	item_uri	cv_id
1	Age	Question	https://example.com/age	4
2	Education level	Question	https://example.com/edu	2
3	Income	Question	https://example.com/inc	NULL
4	Gender	Question	https://example.com/gend	3
5	Job title	Variable	https://example.com/job	2
6	Age Group	Variable	https://example.com/agegroup	4

SURVEY_ITEM table:

survey_id	item_id	item_order
1	1	1
1	2	2
1	3	3
1	4	4
2	5	1
2	6	2
2	3	3

CROSSREF_TYPE table:

crossref_type_id	crossref_type_name
1	Same Variable
2	Related Question
3	Similar Code Set

ITEM_CROSSREF table:

crossref_id	item1_id	item2_id	crossref_type_id
1	1	3	1
2	2	4	2
3	4	5	3
4	1	6	1

CONTROLLED_VOCABULARY table:

cv_id	term	definition
1	Example	example
2	Education	A level of education attainment
3	Gender	A person's gender identity
4	Age Group	A person's age group

Sample SQL Results

Note: Schema has changed now; statements need to be updated

Here are some SQL statements that could be used to fetch different types of reports from the sample data:

1. Get all surveys and their associated items:

```
SELECT s.survey_name, i.item_name, i.item_type
FROM survey s
INNER JOIN survey_item si ON s.survey_id = si.survey_id
INNER JOIN item i ON si.item_id = i.item_id;
```

This query will return a list of all surveys and their associated items, along with the type of each item.

	survey_name	item_name	item_type
▶	National Survey	Age	Question
	National Survey	Education level	Question
	National Survey	Income	Question
	National Survey	Gender	Question
	Regional Survey	Job title	Variable
	Regional Survey	Age	Question
	Regional Survey	Income	Question

2. Get all surveys that include a specific item:

```

SELECT s.survey_name
FROM survey s
INNER JOIN survey_item si ON s.survey_id = si.survey_id
INNER JOIN item i ON si.item_id = i.item_id
WHERE i.item_name = 'Age';

```

This query will return a list of all surveys that include the item with the name 'Age'.

	survey_name	survey_description
▶	National Survey	A national survey of households
	Regional Survey	A regional survey of businesses

3. Get all items and surveys that are related to a specific item:

```

SELECT i2.item_name as 'related item', s.survey_name, ct.crossref_type_name
FROM item_crossref ic
INNER JOIN crossref_type ct ON ic.crossref_type_id = ct.crossref_type_id
INNER JOIN item i ON ic.item1_id=i.item_id
INNER JOIN item i2 ON ic.item2_id=i2.item_id
INNER JOIN survey_item si ON ic.item2_id=si.item_id
INNER JOIN survey s ON si.survey_id=s.survey_id
WHERE i.item_name = 'Age';

```

This query will return a list of all items that are related to the item with the name 'Age'.

	related item	survey_name	crossref_type_name
▶	Age	National Survey	Same Variable
	Age Group	Regional Survey	Same Variable

4. Get all items that are part of a controlled vocabulary:

```

SELECT i.item_name, cv.term, cv.definition
FROM item i
INNER JOIN controlled_vocabulary cv ON i.cv_id = cv.cv_id;

```

This query will return a list of all items along with their associated controlled vocabulary term and definition.

	item_name	term	definition
▶	Age	Income Bracket	A range of income levels
	Education level	Education	A level of education attainment
	Job title	Education	A level of education attainment
	Gender	Gender	A persons gender identity
	Age Group	Age Group	A persons age group

Colectica and Cross-ref schema working together